

QUALITY INDICATORS METASUQUOIA GLYPTOSTROBOIDES OF SEEDS

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Abstract. This article describe about the finding of comprehensive resources on quality of *Metasuquoia Glyptostroboides* seeds on greening and ornamental properties. According to resource the wicked 1000 seeds 25,2 grams and quality rate is 58,2%, which was ground in Tashkent region.

Key words: *Metasuquoia Glyptostroboides*, seeds, quality rate, seed clean, planting

ИНДИКАТОРЫ КАЧЕСТВА СЕМЯН METASUQUOIA GLIPTOSTROBOIDES

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о поиске исчерпывающих исследований качества семян по озеленительным и декоративным свойствам *Metasequoia Glyptostroboides*. По данным исследований, масса 1000 семян 25,2 грамма, а показатель качества составляет 58,2%, которые были пророщены в Ташкентской области.

Ключевые слова: *Metasequoia Glyptostroboides*, семена, показатель качества, очистка семян, посадка

Introduction. At the present time large-scale introductory works are being carried out to enrich the gene pool of plants in our country. One such plant is *Metasuquoia Glyptostroboides*. Nowadays this species is used for landscaping. *Glyptostrobussimon metasecylla* seedlings are suitable for the wide use of their semen quality characteristics.

The results of the researches revealed the qualitative characteristics of *Metasuquoia Glyptostroboides* seeds (seeds of 1,000 seeds). It was found out that 1000 seed weight was 25.2 grams and 58.5% was clean.

The object of the study. *Metasuquoia Glyptostroboides* - family of predecessors belongs to *metasequoia Metasuquoia Glyptostroboides* was an ancient tree, and during the Chaldee, the forest grew in large areas. It is contemporary with dinosaurs. This tree was thought to have vanished. However, in 1941, China's Hubei and Cychuan provinces found its growing trees. From China to the whole world [2].

In 1941, Japanese paleobotanics S.Mikki named *metasecvoya* (Greek meta, intermediate, between) because of the resemblance of the tree found in the stones and the leafy branch of the leaves. The newly found species was very similar to the sequestrant, but there was a difference in morphological signs [3].

Unlike other inflorescences, *Metasuquoia Glyptostroboides* sheds light in the winter The *glyptostrophobic metasevovoy* grows in St. Petersburg, Russia, is well spent winter, but every year, the annual fall of the annual branches is observed.

Metasuquoia Glyptostroboides has a very ornamental horn. The soft spikes are light green and fall in orange in the autumn. Population habitat can be supplemented by gardening, individually planting or grouping[1,4].

Location of the study. Research was carried out in the seeds of *Metasuquoia Glyptostroboides*, growing on the territory of the "Botanical Garden" and "Forestry Research

Institute" of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The climatic conditions of this region are sharply continental, with average annual air temperature +13.5 ° C, the average air temperature + 27 ° C in June and the average air temperature in January is -10 °. Annual precipitation is 114.6 mm, mainly in May, will be. Rainfall is very rare in periods of plant growth. The average relative air humidity is 51%, and the winter is higher in the spring and the summer-eye season is very low. The wind mode falls high in all seasons of the year, from the north to the vegetation and from the south to winter. Wind direction in the region is always changing.

Location of the study. The research was conducted under laboratory conditions. in which research was carried out to determine the weight of seeds and seeds of 1,000 seeds. Seeds of 1000 seeds were found in 3 varieties (100,500 and 1,000 seeds). The seeds were analyzed in 4 variants.

The specimen was spread out flat on the table to determine seed cleanness. Large compounds in it were separated and weight was determined. The samples were then sprinkled in a 1 cm thick square on the table, and the seeds were mixed in the form of seeds and the mixture was stirred until the sample worked.

The sample weight in the research was about 3 grams. The seeds of the seeds in this sample were 1.24 percent, and the pure seeds were 1.76 grams. On the basis of the results, seed cleaning made up 58.5%.

The weight of 1000 seeds is of great importance in the formation of forest: large and heavy seeds have high sowing quality. The seeds are needed to determine the sowing norms. The seeds were harvested in three different sizes.

Seeds of 1000 seeds identified in 500 specimens are weighted by weight of 2 samples.(Table 1)

Table 1.

Weight of 1000 pieces of *Glyptostrobus metasequoia* seeds.

№	Method of determination	Indicators	Average
1	10 и 100 p.	2,9	2,52
2	2 по 500 p.	2,14	
3	1000 p.	2,52	

The weight of 100 seeds was calculated based on the sum of 10 samples weight. When calculating the weight of 1000 seeds, the difference between the two samples can be 5% of the calculated average weight.

The seeds in the experiment conducted, which consists of 100 pieces, however weight 0,26 - 0,31 grams, while an average of 0.29 grams is reached.

The seeds which consists of 500 pieces, however weight 1,05 - 1,09 g, grams while on average amounted to 1,07.

While this section consists of 1000 pieces in grams of the option amounted to 2,52. Go out and seed pieces according to the experience weighted average 2,52 metasekvoyaning by 1000 grams is reached.

Conclusions

Metasuquoia *Glyptostroboides* population a place to live, and other objects can be used in the planting of gardens istiroxat. Because of its specific feature to be different from other types manzaraviylik the season and the show in many different.

The research conducted in Tashkent region in developing growth seeds from the tree however the analysis of quality indicators *Metasequoia Glyptostroboides* was taken up. These seeds 1000 grams seed by 25,2 pieces according to him the weighted average, while the average seed purity by 58,5 %.

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